

Evaluating the Relationship between Reward System and Turnover Intentions among Academic Librarians in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Employee retention remains a critical issue in academic institutions, with turnover intention posing significant challenges to library management. Academic librarians play a crucial role in knowledge dissemination and research support, yet many experience dissatisfaction due to inadequate reward systems. Understanding the relationship between reward systems and turnover intention is essential for effective policy development in university libraries. This study examines the impact of reward systems on the turnover intention of academic librarians in universities in South-west Nigeria.

Method: The study employed a survey research design, targeting a population of 412 academic librarians in South-west Nigerian universities. Using Yamane's formula, a sample size of 205 was determined, and participants were selected through proportionate sampling. A structured and validated questionnaire was used for data collection, achieving a 97% response rate. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including simple and multiple linear regression analyses.

Findings/Results: The results indicate that turnover intention among librarians is relatively high. The study found that the reward system significantly influences librarians' turnover intentions ($R^2 = 0.388$; $\beta = 0.377$, $t = 4.442$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that inadequate reward structures contribute to librarians' decisions to leave their institutions.

Implications: These findings highlight the need for improved reward systems to enhance job satisfaction and retention among academic librarians. The study provides valuable insights for library and university administrators in shaping policies that address workforce stability in academic libraries.

Conclusion: The study confirms that reward systems play a significant role in influencing turnover intention among academic librarians in South-west Nigerian universities. Addressing these concerns is crucial for maintaining a stable and motivated workforce.

Recommendations: To mitigate turnover intentions, university and library administrators should implement policies that enhance reward systems. Structured incentive programs, competitive remuneration, and career development opportunities should be prioritized to retain skilled librarians and improve library services.

Keywords: Reward system, Turnover intention, Academic librarians, Universities, Nigeria.

Introduction

Employees are regarded as valuable assets for achieving organizational growth and national development. Therefore, an organization's sustainability is mainly dependent on its ability to leverage human resources for sustainable competitive advantage and organizational success. A major source of concern for organizations is the growing rate of employee turnover intention, which is simply described as an employee's willingness and desire to quit an organization's employment. In recent years, there have been numerous reports of librarians and other professionals leaving public and privately owned institutions due to a number of issues, the majority of which are related to dissatisfaction

with the reward system, among other factors such as organizational justice, work-life balance, organizational culture, leadership style, and job satisfaction. According to studies, an increasing number of librarians intend to quit their current jobs in coming years (Oloyede & Soyemi, 2022; Akpom & Ibegbulam, 2023).

Turnover intention, though inevitable, has detrimental effects on organizations, particularly when highly talented employees are involved (Bhagwandeem, 2021). The loss of human capital and knowledge, disruption of programs, and the costs associated with recruiting, selecting, and training new employees are substantial non-monetary and monetary costs of turnover intentions for organizations. To gain a competitive edge and achieve organizational goals, organizations must focus on attracting, motivating, and retaining qualified employees through rewards.

Reward systems play a crucial role in human resource management by recruiting, motivating, and retaining employees (Eerde, 2015). They encompass the planning, policy formation, and administration of all forms of compensation provided to employees in exchange for their time and services. Extrinsic and intrinsic rewards are the two types of rewards also interchangeably referred to as monetary and non-monetary rewards (Mustafa & Ali, 2019). Extrinsic rewards refer to external forms of compensation that are not directly tied to the nature of the job itself. These include salary, cash incentives, fringe benefits, training and development opportunities, and promotions (Omokorede, 2017). In contrast, intrinsic rewards are non-financial and stem from the personal fulfilment and psychological satisfaction an employee gains from performing their job, such as a sense of achievement, recognition, and personal growth. Fernando and Ranaweera (2019) described non-financial rewards as tangible rewards, social practices, or job-related elements used by organizations to stimulate workers devoid of cash payment. Examples include verbal recognition, personal fulfilment from task completion, acquisition of new skills, and the sense of importance as a team member.

Reward is one organizational component that both employers and employees value because it determines what an organization is willing to offer, which has a direct impact on what employees are willing to give in return. As a result, the reward system is critical in determining the employer-employee relationship (Franco-Santos & Gomez-Mejia, 2015). Employees bring a diverse range of skills, aspirations, and expectations to organisations and anticipate recognition and equitable compensation from employers in exchange for their time, effort, knowledge, skills, creativity, and energy. To enhance

effectiveness, reward systems should be strategically designed to be attractive, cost-efficient, and fair, while aligning with the broader objectives of the organization.

In the context of libraries in Nigeria, turnover intentions among librarians have emerged as a significant concern, affecting the sustainability of libraries, service quality, and overall performance. This study aims to investigate how reward system influences the turnover intentions of librarians in federal, state and private universities in South-West Nigeria. By examining this relationship, the study seeks to provide insights that can inform strategies for improving retention and enhancing the effectiveness of library services in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Employee turnover intention is a significant concern for organizations globally, including libraries in Nigeria, where high turnover rates are evident (Oyetola 2013; Nyamubarwa, 2013; Oloyede & Soyemi, 2022). Librarians with turnover intentions, exhibit counterproductive behaviors such as absenteeism, lateness and reduced effectiveness, which negatively impact library services ((Masenya, 2019; Xiong & Wen, 2020; Soyemi & Oloyede, 2022). Evidence from the study of Nzelum, Unegbu, Nworie and Irunegbo (2019) indicates that reward system satisfaction enhances job satisfaction and reduces turnover intentions among librarians. However, despite these findings, turnover rates continue to rise. This study seeks to investigate how reward system satisfaction influences turnover intentions among librarians in university libraries in South-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of the turnover intention of librarians in university libraries in South-West Nigeria?
2. What is the level of satisfaction of librarians in university libraries in South-West Nigeria with the reward system?

Hypothesis

H¹ Reward system does not significantly influence the turnover intention of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Literature Review

This study builds upon expectancy theory (Vroom, 1964), which emphasizes the significance of employees' expectations of rewards in motivating behavior. It posits that

when employees anticipate acknowledgment and reward for their efforts, they are more likely to perform effectively. Conversely, if rewards fall short of expectations, it may lead to dissatisfaction and intentions to leave. Reward system is the decision-making activity involved in the allocation of compensation and benefits to employees in exchange for their contribution to the organization (Pratheepkanth, 2011).

Eerde (2015) describes reward systems as policies and procedures through which organizations administer employee rewards. Nzelum, Unegbu, Nworie, and Irunegbo (2019) simply describe reward systems as pay-offs for performance. In credence, Omolawal and Bawalla (2023) describe a basic reward system as an employee's salary or wage, which may be computed hourly, monthly, bi-weekly, or yearly. Employers' capacity to recruit, retain, and reward adequately qualified and competent employees may be influenced by the organization's reward system. For the purpose of this study, Compensation, Benefits, Performance Recognition, and Career Opportunities are highlighted as variables of reward system that correlate with the turnover intentions of librarians.

Various studies have shown that reward systems are human resource management practices that play a vital role in attracting, retaining, and motivating employees (Gautam, 2020), influencing job performance and positive attitude (Unegbu, Babalola & Basahuwa, 2020; Dina & Olowosoke, 2018; Okoye, 2017), employee commitment and engagement (Hamid, Sadiqe & Muzaffar, 2015; Ali, Amin, & Hamid, 2016; Nazir, Shafi & Tran, 2016), job satisfaction (Udo-Anyanwu & Amadi, 2020) and also predicting employees turnover intentions (Hardianto, et al, 2019; Akhigbe & Onuoha, 2021). A study conducted to assess the impact of meaningful work on happiness at work and turnover intention among 937 professionals in Mexico revealed that meaningful work, feeling appreciated by coworkers, and enjoyment of daily tasks which are variables of reward significantly influence employee happiness at work and turnover intention (Charles-Leija, et al, 2023)

The relationship between reward system and employee turnover intention has been examined in several studies and there are indications that extrinsic rewards correlate more with employee turnover intention (A'yuninnisa & Saptoto, 2015; Azeez & Lawal, 2016). Other studies suggest that intrinsic reward is effective and may have more influence on employee motivation and turnover intentions (Fernando & Ranaweera, 2019; Dong, 2020). Perhaps extrinsic and intrinsic rewards have varied effects on employee motivation. In credence, Mendis (2017) opined that financial rewards tend to gratify employees by offering monetary benefits while non-monetary rewards satisfy employees'

ego and self-actualization requirements and desires. This implies that extrinsic and intrinsic rewards are significant to both employees and employers, hence the need for a total reward system.

The concept of a total reward system according to Neal (1998), encompasses all an employee values in an employment relationship. This holistic approach unifies both extrinsic and intrinsic rewards into a comprehensive whole, to attract, motivate, and retain employees within an organization. Since the various aspects of the total reward system are interconnected, a total reward strategy must be comprehensive rather than relying on just one or two elements of reward (Adebisi and Oladipo, 2015). Compensation/remuneration, benefits, work-life balance, performance recognition, and career opportunities are all crucial elements of the total reward system (Gautam, 2020; Turnea & Prodan, 2020). Therefore, organizations that intend to deal with employee retention, deliberately need to focus on a total compensation system.

Findings from various studies have suggested that both internal and extrinsic factors play a role in improving employee behavior, productivity, and performance and lowering the likelihood of turnover intention (Iyke-Ofoedu, Nwankwo & Okechukwu, 2023; Nzelum, Unegbu, Nworie & Irunebo, 2019; Afzal, Ali & Saleem, 2015). In agreement, reports of previous studies reveal that extrinsic and intrinsic rewards have a significant influence on employee turnover intention (Arianto & Syihabudhin, 2018; Mendis, 2017; Afzal, Ali, & Saleem, 2015 and Akgunduz, Adan, & Alkan, 2020). The study by Azeez and Lawal (2016) which investigated the effect of financial reward on employee turnover among staff of Lagos State University, reported a significant positive relationship between financial reward and employee turnover intentions. Inferring that, the better the financial reward, the lower the turnover intentions of employees. In the same vein, Fapohunda (2012) also asserts that good wages improve productivity and decrease employees' turnover intention.

There is a high rate of turnover intentions among librarians globally (Hamzat et al., 2020; Masenya, 2020; Oloyede & Soyemi, 2022; Fyn, et al., 2023) and the key causes of librarian turnover as identified by Fyn, Heady, Foster-Kaufman, and Hosier (2019) are library administration, morale, direct supervisors and rewards. These factors evoke the highest degrees of non-satisfaction among librarians who intend to quit their jobs. Afzal, Ali, and Saleem (2015) emphasized on employee satisfaction with reward systems as it stimulates desirable behaviors and suppresses unfavorable ones such as lack of commitment, absenteeism, turnover intentions, and turnover (Sanm & Nazir, 2022).

According to Nzelum, Unegbu, Nworie, and Irunebo (2019), reward systems have a significant relationship with librarians' job satisfaction. Their study revealed that librarians are dissatisfied with their remuneration, benefits, and salaries.

A study conducted by Okoye (2017) to investigate the effect of the reward system on academic librarians' job performance in South-East, Nigeria, found that most librarians were unsatisfied with their salaries, which affected their performance on the job. Similarly, findings from the study of Mahamoud (2022) indicated that reward has a significant effect on employee performance. Dina and Olowosoke (2018) also affirmed that reward systems with an emphasis on extrinsic rewards such as salary in Nigerian universities are unsatisfactory. However, some indications motivated employees tend to perform better at work (Unegbu, Babalola, & Basahuwa, 2020).

Following reports from the studies reviewed, it is apparent that the reward system significantly influences organizational behavior and outcomes. While Dina and Olowosoke (2018) emphasized, that financial benefits have a positive effect on library personnel motivation, library infrastructure, conducive work environment, unbiased reward system, and employee empowerment are motivational factors that can enhance job satisfaction and performance of librarians (Unegbu, Babalola & Basahuwa, 2020; Omeluzor, Pelemo, Agbawe, Onasote & Abayomi 2017). Generally, when librarians are satisfied with their reward systems, it positively impacts their job satisfaction, leading to lower intentions to leave their organizations. Consequently, library administrators must embrace a total reward system, review policies regarding rewards, and ensure prompt payment of salaries and increments when necessary. Total reward systems attract, and retain competent employees, and influence organizational behaviour.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design. The target population included 412 academic librarians from fifty-three (53) universities including federal, state and private in South-West Nigeria. A sample size of 205 was determined using Yamane's formula. Proportionate random sampling technique was employed to select the librarians from each university. Data were collected using a structured and validated questionnaire, with Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the constructs ranging from 0.70 to 0.91. All 205 distributed questionnaires were retrieved, with 199 found usable, yielding a response rate of 97%. The analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistics, including simple and multiple linear regression.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	97	48.7
	Female	102	51.3
	Total	199	100.0
Age group	Below 30	33	16.6
	31-40	57	28.6
	41-50	79	39.7
	51-60	30	15.1
	Above 60	-	-
	Total	199	100.0
Educational Qualification	BSC/BA/BLIS/BLS/HND	85	42.7
	MSc/MLIS/MLS/MA/MBA/PGD	73	36.7
	PhD	41	20.6
	Total	199	100.0
Years worked in the library	0-5	39	19.6
	5-10	25	12.5
	10-15	98	49.5
	16-20	17	8.5
	21-25	11	5.5
	26-30	9	4.4
	Above 31	-	-
	Total	199	100.0

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, indicating that female librarians (51.3%) slightly outnumber their male counterparts (48.7%) in universities across South-West Nigeria. Most librarians are middle-aged (39.7%), with smaller proportions of older individuals (15.1%), and younger respondents aged 31-40 years (28.6%) and below 30 years (16.6%). Educationally, 42.7% hold B.Sc./B.A. degrees, 36.7% possess MSc or equivalent qualifications, and 20.6% have PhDs. Regarding professional experience, nearly half (49.5%) have 10-15 years in the field, with smaller

percentages having longer tenures (16-20 years: 8.5%, 21-25 years: 5.5%, 26-30 years: 4.4%), reflecting a substantial presence of experienced librarians in these institutions.

Research question one: What is the level of the turnover intention of librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 2
Level of Turnover Intention of Librarians in University Libraries

<i>Items</i>	VHL	HL	SHL	L	VL	Mean	Std.
	Freq.	Freq.	Freq.	Freq.	Freq.	(\bar{x})	(SD)
The level to which	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)		
Job satisfaction						3.35	0.95
My job does not fulfill my personal needs	15 (7.6)	30 (15.0)	55 (27.6)	79 (39.8)	20 (10.0)	3.57	1.09
My current job has a negative effect on my well-being	-	11 (5.5)	71 (35.7)	107 (53.8)	10 (5.0)	2.53	1.07
Thoughts of quitting						1.00	1.01
I am considering leaving my job	19 (9.5)	29 (14.6)	47 (23.6)	73 (36.7)	31 (15.6)	2.32	1.08
I do not look forward to another day at work	-	-	21 (10.5)	85 (42.7)	93 (46.7)	1.27	1.13
Costs of quitting						3.23	1.09
Fear of the unknown prevents me from quitting	51 (25.6)	73 (36.7)	33 (16.6)	18 (9.0)	22 (11.0)	3.53	1.07
Benefits from my current job prevent me from quitting	29 (14.6)	44 (22.1)	39 (19.6)	70 (35.2)	8 (4.0)	3.43	1.11
Search for alternatives						3.57	1.15
I actively search for alternative jobs	11 (5.5)	41 (20.6)	77 (38.9)	70 (35.2)	-	3.27	1.13
I plan to start a business	55 (27.6)	71 (35.7)	13 (6.5)	39 (19.6)	21 10.5	4.18	1.18
Probability of finding another job						4.25	1.03
More university libraries are being established	73 (36.7)	81 (40.7)	40 (21.1)	5 (2.5)	-	4.57	1.09
I can get another job	61 (30.6)	93 (46.3)	45 (22.6)	-	-	4.89	1.11
Evaluating alternatives						3.51	1.03
I will accept another job at the same compensation level should I be offered	11 (5.5)	44 (22.1)	53 (26.6)	70 (35.2)	21 (10.5)	3.27	1.13
I compare my present reward to that of other universities around me	58 (29.1)	51 (25.6)	49 (24.6)	-	41 (20.6)	3.83	1.07
Average Overall Mean						3.39	1.10

Source: Field Survey (2022)

KEY: *VHL=Very High Level, HL=High Level, SHL=Somewhat High Level, LL=Low Level, VLL=Very Low Level***Decision Rule: if mean is 1 to 1.79= Very Low Level, 1.80 to 2.59= Low Level, 2.60 to 3.39= Somewhat High Level, 3.40 to 4.19= High Level, 4.20 to 5 = Very High Level*

Table 2 shows that the level of turnover intention among librarians in universities in South-West Nigeria is somewhat high (\bar{x} = 3.39, SD= 1.10). A significant proportion of librarians consider leaving their jobs, due to high levels of job dissatisfaction linked to unmet personal needs (\bar{x} = 3.57) and negative effects on well-being (\bar{x} = 3.53). Despite this dissatisfaction, many remain in their jobs due to the benefits they receive (\bar{x} = 3.43) and fear of the unknown (\bar{x} = 3.53), reflecting the perceived cost of quitting.

Active job searches (\bar{x} = 3.27) and entrepreneurial aspirations (\bar{x} = 4.18) are prevalent among librarians, indicating a desire for better fulfillment and financial improvement. Librarians also perceive increased job availability with the establishment of more university libraries (\bar{x} = 4.57), enhancing their chances of finding new employment (\bar{x} = 4.89). Furthermore, willingness to accept jobs at the same compensation level (\bar{x} = 3.27) and comparisons of rewards with other institutions (\bar{x} = 3.83) suggest a readiness to quit. However, despite a low level of actual turnover behavior (\bar{x} = 2.32), the substantial perceived cost of resigning (\bar{x} = 3.53) and active evaluation of alternatives (\bar{x} = 3.83) indicate that librarians are only managing their current jobs but have the intention to leave or start a business.

Table 3

Level of Librarians' Satisfaction with Their Reward Systems

<i>Items</i>	VH Freq. (%)	H Freq. (%)	SH Freq. (%)	L Freq. (%)	VL Freq. (%)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. (SD)
The level to which							
Compensation						3.23	1.25
My salary is satisfactory for the work I do	-	-	54 (27.1)	113 (56.8)	32 (16.1)	1.44	1.16
I earn the same with that of similar jobs in other libraries	-	-	66 (33.2)	94 (47.2)	39 (20.6)	1.54	1.16
Compensation is favorably reviewed from time to time	21 (10.5)	92 (46.2)	48 (24.1)	38 (19.0)	-	3.39	1.06
Salary increments are decided in a fair manner	13 (6.5)	31 (15.6)	84 (42.2)	55 (27.5)	16 (8.0)	3.35	1.37
Benefits						3.03	1.16

I get medical care/schemes from my organization	33 (16.6)	149 (74.9)	17 (8.5)	- -	- -	3.88	1.31
I have the opportunity to go on sabbatical leave	-	-	63 (31.6)	97 (48.8)	39 (19.6)	1.73	1.75
I have the opportunity to go on study leave	64 (32.2)	111 (55.8)	17 (8.5)	7 (3.5)	-	3.75	1.93
Annual leave days are available to me	169 (84.9)	20 (10.0)	10 (5.0)	-	-	4.92	3.03
Recognition						2.35	1.12
I get credit for my contribution to the institution	19 (9.6)	15 (7.5)	38 (19.0)	51 (25.6)	76 (38.2)	2.97	2.99
I am praised regularly for my work performance	-	-	115 (57.8)	27 (13.6)	57 (28.6)	1.38	1.21
I get constructive and honest feedback on my performance	-	49 (24.6)	22 (11.2)	67 (33.6)	61 (30.6)	2.15	2.78
I get formal recognition for a job well done	-	71 (35.7)	20 (10.0)	88 (44.2)	20 (10.0)	2.95	2.08
Career Opportunities						3.55	1.12
I receive training on the job	78 (39.3)	73 (36.7)	18 (9.0)	14 (7.0)	16 (8.0)	3.41	1.99
There are opportunities for advancement in this job	77 (38.7)	21 (10.5)	45 (22.6)	53 (26.6)	3 (1.5)	3.59	2.09
There are chances of getting ahead on this job	15 (7.5)	24 (12.0)	104 (52.3)	17 (8.5)	30 (15.0)	3.95	1.10
There are equal opportunities for promotions	-	17 (8.5)	55 (27.6)	109 (54.8)	18 (9.0)	2.13	1.97
Average Weighted Mean						3.25	1.42

Source: Field Survey (2022)

KEY: *VH=Very high, H=High, SH=somewhat high, L=Low, VL=Very low***Decision Rule: if mean is 1 to 1.79= Very Low, 1.80 to 2.59= Low, 2.60 to 3.39= Somewhat High, 3.40 to 4.19= High, 4.20 to 5 = Very High*

Table 3 indicates that librarians in South-West Nigeria exhibit a somewhat high level of satisfaction with their workplace reward systems ($\bar{x} = 3.25$, $SD = 1.42$). While compensation is rated as somewhat high ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), satisfaction with salary is very low ($\bar{x} = 1.44$), particularly when compared to similar positions in other libraries ($\bar{x} = 1.54$). This suggests that librarians are dissatisfied with perceived salary competitiveness and may be inclined to leave for better compensation.

Librarians benefit from organizational packages, particularly medical care ($\bar{x} = 3.88$) and study leave ($\bar{x} = 3.75$), but opportunities for sabbatical leave are limited ($\bar{x} = 1.73$). Additionally, annual leave availability is highly rated ($\bar{x} = 4.92$). However, recognition for contributions is low ($\bar{x} = 2.35$), with poor feedback ($\bar{x} = 2.15$) and limited formal recognition for good performance ($\bar{x} = 2.95$). This indicates that librarians feel undervalued, which may undermine motivation.

Remarkably, career opportunities for librarians are generally rated high ($\bar{x} = 3.55$), with opportunities for advancement ($\bar{x} = 3.59$), training ($\bar{x} = 3.41$), and chances of career progression ($\bar{x} = 3.95$) ranking well. Overall, the average weighted mean ($\bar{x} = 3.22$, SD = 1.42) suggests a somewhat high level of satisfaction with the reward system, though improvements, especially in compensation and recognition, are necessary. Given the critical role of rewards in job satisfaction, motivation, and retention, enhancing the reward system could improve overall employee satisfaction.

H¹: The reward system does not significantly influence the turnover intention of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Table 4: *Influence of Reward System on Turnover Intention of Librarians in Universities in South-West, Nigeria*

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19471.330	2	7109.611	36.401	.000 ^b
Residual	7411.553	196	41.011		
Total	26882.883	198			
	R=.359	R Square= .388		Adj. R Square= .385	
Coefficients					
Construct	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta (β)	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	41.271	2.488		11.654	.000
Compensation	.347	.911	.313	4.339	.013
Benefits	.344	.201	.411	6.511	.000
Recognition	.391	.097	.387	6.435	.000
Career opportunities	.349	.301	.352	5.903	.000

Dependent Variable: Turnover intention.

Source: Field Survey 2022 Note: β = Standardized Coefficient, significant at 0.05

The regression analysis result in Table 4 reveals that there is a significant influence of reward system ($F_{(2,196)} = 36.401$, $R^2 = .388$, $P \leq .05$) on the turnover intention of librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. The result further depicts that all the indicators of the reward system have a strong significant influence on turnover intention, with benefits ($\beta = .411$, $P \leq .05$), having the highest percentage of variation of influence (41.1%). This means that university libraries where these indicators are not adequately catered for are likely to experience higher rates of turnover intention among their workers. Following the evidence of the significant influence reward has on turnover intentions of librarians the simple hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The reported somewhat high level ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 1.10$) of turnover intention among librarians in this study indicates a significant concern for the retention of librarians in universities in South-West Nigeria. This report corresponds with previous studies which reported a high rate of turnover intention among librarians in the South-west (Idiegbeyanose, Opeke, Nwokeoma, 2018; Soyemi & Oloyede, 2022) and South-south Nigeria (Aiyebilehin, Odiachi & Omoregie, 2020).

Also, a study carried out in private universities in Osun state, revealed that 66% of librarians and information professionals have the intention of quitting their jobs as soon as an opportunity shows up (Hamzat, Abata-Ebire, Ogunjinmi & Babarinde, 2020). Although librarians indicated having low thoughts of quitting, many remain in their jobs out of fear of uncertainty. Nevertheless, their belief in the potential costs of leaving, combined with active job searches and confidence in finding new jobs, indicates a significant level of consideration regarding alternatives.

Sadly, these findings imply that many librarians intend to leave due to the dissatisfaction and perceived availability of better prospects elsewhere. This is in tandem with the findings of Aiyebilehin, Odiachi, and Omoregie (2020) and Ahmad (2023) who asserted that employees are more likely to leave their jobs if they have job options available. Consequently, librarians who have the intention to leave are a concern to library administrators and university management. This is because employees who wish to quit the organization perform less productively (Charles-Leija, Castro, Toledo & Ballesteros-Valdés, 2023). The high turnover intention suggests that librarians are less likely to make

meaningful contributions to the growth and success of the library and this can negatively affect the quality-of-service delivery.

The study highlights that while librarians generally express a somewhat high level of satisfaction with the reward system within their organizations, areas such as compensation, benefits, and recognition receive lower mean scores, indicating potential turnover intentions if improvements are not made. This finding resonates with a previous study on school teachers in Indonesia, which linked rewards directly to turnover intention (Hardianto *et al.*, 2019). Poor salaries are identified as a major factor leading to turnover intention among academic librarians in Zimbabwe (Nyamubarwa, 2013).

Librarians in Nigeria also consider leaving their jobs and the profession due to demographic factors, particularly low pay (Onwubiko, 2020). A more recent study conducted among academic librarians in the United States revealed that 44.4% of librarians contemplate leaving their jobs, with a significant majority of 69.73% citing compensation and benefits as a primary reason for considering leaving (Fyn, Kaufman & Heady, 2023). These reflect a broader trend of dissatisfaction with income among librarians and motivation to seek better opportunities (Oyetola, 2013; Okoye, 2017).

While the study highlighted concerns about librarians' satisfaction with rewards and job intentions, Udo-Anyanwu and Amadi (2020) found a positive correlation between extrinsic and intrinsic rewards and job satisfaction among librarians in Imo state, suggesting they are content with their rewards and overall job satisfaction. However, the situation is not the same for librarians in other regions. The high effect of reward on the turnover intention of librarians in South-West, Nigeria is consistent with global research indicating that reward drives employee motivation, job satisfaction, and, ultimately turnover intention (Turnea & Prodan, 2020; Mustafa, Ghulam, Ali & Noorina, 2019; Mendis, 2017 and Azeez & Lawal, 2016). This shows that reward is an important variable in the lives of employees as they depend on income emanating from compensation and benefits to meet their own and family needs.

The outcome of this study is in line with the assertion of Afzal, Ali, and Saleem (2015) and that of Arianto and Syihabudhin (2018) who noted that satisfaction with workplace rewards invariably motivate desired employee behaviors and attitudes such as commitment, performance, and productivity. On the other hand, poor rewards result in dissatisfaction among librarians (Nzelum, Unegbu, Nworie, & Irunegbo, 2019).

The study by Omokorede (2017) showed that an appropriate reward system discourages negative behavior such as low commitment, absenteeism, turnover intention, and turnover. When an employee's reward is delayed, denied, or perceived as unfair, morale is negatively affected, leading to what Omokorede described as unproductive performance and, in extreme cases, a high percentage of employee turnovers. Reward is among the possible reasons why an employee is at work and has the propensity to engender a high level of turnover intention among employees unless adequately treated.

From the above assertions, it is noticeable that reward has a significant influence on librarians' job performance and turnover intentions. Employees' inclination to leave the organization decreases as they perceive more positive aspects of it (Zanak *et al.*, 2024). As indicated in a study conducted by Udo-Anyanwu and Amadi (2020), academic librarians in Imo state are delighted with their jobs as there exists a positive relationship between extrinsic rewards, intrinsic rewards, and job satisfaction of library staff, respectively. Employees who are unsatisfied with an organization's reward system, on the other hand, are more likely to be dissatisfied with their jobs and to consider quitting. However, to promote academic librarians' happiness and dedication to the profession, a strong and effective motivation is necessary at all levels, departments, and units of the library (Oyetola, 2013) as this will eliminate the desire to quit.

Consequent upon the findings from this study, which was carried out to examine the influence of reward system on librarians' turnover intention in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria, it can be concluded that the reward system influenced the turnover intention of librarians in this study. This underscores the critical importance of addressing the issue of rewards to retain talent within the librarian profession.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study emphasizes the urgent need to improve reward and retention strategies for librarians in university libraries across South-West Nigeria. While there is some satisfaction with current reward systems, major concerns remain regarding compensation, benefits, and recognition. Without adequate improvement in these areas, high turnover intention is likely to persist, eventually leading to actual turnover.

To address these concerns, university management and library administrators must prioritize employee retention by implementing strategies to enhance job satisfaction and reduce turnover intention. Competitive compensation packages should be regularly reviewed, and a culture of recognition should be fostered, with formal programs

acknowledging librarians' contributions. Upgrading all reward system indicators is essential to positively influence turnover intention in university libraries.

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